

Academic Staff Empowerment and Quality Assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between academic staff empowerment and quality assurance in the College of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria. The ex-post facto design was used for the study. A simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 150 academic staff in the study area. A questionnaire entitled "Academic Staff Empowerment and Quality Assurance Questionnaire (ASEQAQ)" was used to obtain data. The questionnaire was structured based on a 4-point Likert scale format with 15 items. The data obtained through the questionnaire administration were coded and transferred to SPSS for analysis using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis. The results obtained showed that academic staff empowerment indices such as compensation and exposure to new opportunities correlate to quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. It was therefore recommended among others that, academic staff compensation should be treated as important as possible, promotion of academic staff should be prioritized and with financial benefits, academic staff should be constantly trained in both content and pedagogy.

Keywords: Academic, assurance, college of education, empowerment, quality, staff.

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Introduction

The success of every academic programme in the tertiary institutions of learning is rested on the driving forces that stir up tasks performance and higher productivity leading to the entire quality assurance. The roles of tertiary institutions are to train and produce adequate manpower with higher intellectual capacity for self-reliance and the development of society. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004) states that the goal of Colleges of Education (as teacher Education institutions) is to produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for primary schools. This goal can only be achieved through effective teaching and research by the academic staff, and these quality assurance practices are to some extent dependent upon academic staff empowerment. Therefore, empowering staff is imperative for educational quality and the entire quality assurance.

Quality assurance is seen as how quality is promoted, assured and maintained in an educational institution. According to Okon and Ushie (2016) quality assurance connotes a systematic process of ascertaining whether educational services are meeting the organizational and societal requirements. This quality assurance can only be ascertained through effective teaching and learning, production of quality graduates that would meet up the needs of society. Following this, Etor and Osim (2014) buttressed the fact that quality assurance is an expectation of the overall outcome of curriculum implementation through instructional effectiveness usually evident in students' academic performances. Quality assurance in teacher education institutions has been a permanent issue and a great concern in the educational system. This is so because a cursory look at the quality of some NCE graduates or teachers appears that the quality of service is not meeting the need of the educational industry and that of society. Ebuara (2015) opined that quality assurance is recognized as being essential to knowledge, economic growth and active participation within the society using higher education institutions as potential engines. But this is not the case in recent times in our Colleges of Education.

Besides, the teaching commitment of some academic staff in Colleges of Education in Cross River State is ineffective. This is evident in the quality of NCE teachers they produce year after year to teach in our primary schools. In line with this, Ndifon (2017) observed that the image of primary school (NCE) teachers has shown that they are incapable of meeting the social and economic needs of society. This is why Rugai and Agih (2007) averred that quality assurance in education involves setting standards for various activities to be carried out in the course of producing graduates in educational training institutions. To compound further, some academic staff feel reluctant to teach whole-heartedly due to poor condition of service and inefficient empowerment indices. This means that, for every academic staff to function effectively, there must be efficient empowerment and support strategies as driving forces as evident in most pieces of literature. It, therefore, appears that the lagging in quality assurance or maintenance is traceable to inefficient empowerment indices such as academic staff compensation and exposure to new opportunities in the institutions. Wonah, Egbula and Ubi (2015) averred that for every education organization to attract and maintain a workforce it must adequately make provision for employees' welfare packages.

Academic staff empowerment is a human resource development or a motivational strategy where employees are allowed to update knowledge, have some degree of autonomy, be involved in decision-making and enjoy some compensational benefits for effective service delivery. According to Ofesebe and Chukwuma (2015), academic staff empowerment is the process whereby the academic staff are inculcated with the right competencies that will enable them to improve their teaching and functions effectively in the school environment. Empowering academic staff in the world of school would improve their status, teaching effectiveness, quality instruction and total quality assurance in the higher institutions of learning. In the light of this, the study "Academic staff empowerment and quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria" becomes imperative.

Quality assurance in contemporary society has become a permanent issue and a matter of discourse in our tertiary education industry. This has equally attracted the attention of concerned individuals, scholars, researchers and educators. In an attempt to maintain quality, quality assurance units and departments have been established in Colleges of Education in Cross River State to maintain a standard, achieve quality teaching and learning and training of qualified teachers to teach in our primary school system. But the reverse is the case in recent times. A cursory look at the quality of NCE teachers churned into the society shows that quality lagging in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. There has been an outcry by the Cross River State Ministry of Education and State Universal Basic Education Board during the last 2018/2019 recruitment of NCE teachers in the primary schools over the alarming rate of incompetency in some primary school teachers. Researchers have also lamented the negligence and lack of concern of some academic staff in encouraging the learners through effective teaching and learning.

Despite the government's efforts in funding the Colleges of Education for the achievement of quality assurance and maintenance, the situation remains the same and unsolved. These problems may be attributed to a lack of academic staff empowerment such as compensation and exposure to new opportunities. Academic staff empowerment could serve as a critical tool to achieving quality assurance in Colleges of Education but this is not effective in the institutions. These problems necessitated the study to determine the relationship between academic staff empowerment and quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria. Academic staff empowerment is a set of strategies that stir up and sustain the activities of workers to bring out their potentials for efficient instructional performance leading to quality assurance. Such empowerment variables include compensation, opportunities for new knowledge and advancement, recognition and other indices. Abdul-Jaleel (2013) conducted a study on the influence of compensation on teachers' job performance. The results of the study revealed that the job of teachers increases significantly when there is some kind of compensation. This means that if teachers are given some compensatory packages, they have satisfaction with their job and will put in their best. Denga cited in Uko (2014) noted that teachers are human beings with psychological needs which must be met to boost their morale for self-investment. Ndifon (2017) found that intrinsic motivation in terms of compensation makes teachers do better in the discharge of their duty and increase their productivity. Akeke and Ofem (2016) observed that the provision of incentives/compensation to staff has a positive relationship with quality assurance.

Atanda (2016) found that compensation and welfare packages promote the task performance of academic staff. The author added that they are potent factors in determining their input into the productive effort. In conjunction with this, Atanda (2014) called on the government to empower school personnel through welfare packages to ensure quality education for sustainable development. Wonah, Egbula and Ubi (2015) averred that the provision of welfare package to employees promotes the social and organizational conditions of workers and impacts their productivity. Ekpiken and Asuquo (2015) studied the relationship between funding of in-service training and school goal achievement and higher productivity. The result was positive. Tulgan cited in Ndifon (2017) maintained that teachers want to be exposed to new

opportunities that come with having their work recognized and as a result, they would naturally maximize opportunities to showcase their creative talents. Akeke and Ofem (2016) observed that the organization must provide need-based training and education to its staff to enable them to become competent in handling their present or future assigned tasks.

Etor and Osim (2014) found that teacher empowerment in terms of providing opportunities for training relates positively to quality assurance in school. Babalola (2009) averred that managers' main task is to develop a productive workplace with or through people; the manager should motivate his or her team both individually and collectively so that the product of the workplace is maintained. Udofot (2005) observed that teachers need relevant skills and specific knowledge of the subject matter to teach effectively. They also need conceptual knowledge of the dynamics of the social system and social change. It is therefore the responsibility of the school administrator and the government to provide new opportunities for teachers to perform maximally and stay on the job. The author maintained that without the opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills and apply them, teachers' day to day work would likely experience frustration and demoralization. This study sought to determine the relationship between academic staff empowerment and quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the purposes of the study are to examine:

1. The relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance
2. The relationship between exposure to new opportunities and quality assurance

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance.
2. Exposure to new opportunities does not significantly relate to quality assurance.

Methods

The design used for the study was Ex-post facto design. This design was found suitable because the variables under study had already existed without manipulation. The design also investigates the relationship between variables. The study was conducted in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria. The population consisted of 202 and 350 academic staff in Cross River State College of Education, Akamkpa and Federal College of Education Obudu, Cross River State respectively, totalling 552 academic staff. The sample size consisted of 150 academic staff (70 from COE Akamkpa and 82 from FCE Obudu) selected through a simple random technique. A researcher-developed questionnaire with 15 items entitled "Academic Staff Empowerment and Quality Assurance Questionnaire (ASEQAQ)" was used to obtain data. The instrument was validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation and was administered to 150 academic staff in the study area. The administration yielded a 100% result. The obtained data were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance. Table 1 showed that at .05 level of significance and degree of freedom 148, the critical r-value is .159. The calculated r-value obtained in establishing the relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance is .53 ($p < .05$). The calculated r-value was seen to be greater than the critical r-value with the obtained significant value less than the .05 level of significance used in the study. With these results, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance was rejected. It was alternately accepted that there is a significant relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. The significant r-value was positive indicating a positive correlation between the two variables. It showed that increase in academic staff compensation will bring about quality assurance and maintenance in colleges of education in Cross River State, Nigeria

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance (N = 150)

Variables	Mean	SD	Rxy	Sig.
Academic compensation (X)	18.12	1.97		
Quality assurance (Y)	17.83	1.76	0.53*	0.00

* $p < .05$; $df = 148$; critical $r = .159$

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between exposure to new opportunities and quality assurance. Table 2 indicated that at a .05 level of significance and degree of freedom 148, the critical r-value is .159. The calculated r-value obtained in establishing the relationship between exposure to new opportunities and quality assurance is .49 ($p < .05$). The calculated r-value was seen to be greater than the critical r-value with the obtained significant value less than the .05 level of significance used in the study. With these results, the null hypothesis which stated that exposure to new opportunities does not significantly relate to quality assurance was rejected. It was alternately accepted that exposure to new opportunities significantly relates to quality assurance. The significant r-value was positive indicating a positive correlation between the two variables. It showed that the provision and exposure of academic staff to new opportunities will promote quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of the relationship between exposure to new opportunities and quality assurance (N = 150)

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	rxy	Sig.
Exposure to new opportunities (X)	17.09	1.43		
Quality assurance (Y)	17.83	1.76	0.49*	0.000

* $p < .05$; $df = 148$; critical $r = .159$

Discussion of findings

The result of hypothesis one as presented in table 1 revealed that there is a significant relationship between academic staff compensation and quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. In line with these findings, Abdul-Jaleel (2013) observed that job of academic staff increases significantly when there are some forms of compensation. Denga cited in Uko (2014) noted that teachers' needs must be met to boost their morale for self-investment in their job. This means that if compensatory benefits such as to promote with pay, allowances etc. are well met academic staff in higher institutions would work efficiently to achieve quality assurance. Ndifon (2017) affirmed that empowerment in terms of compensation makes teachers do better in their job. Also, Akeke and Ofem (2016) found that the provision of compensation to staff has a positive relationship with quality assurance. This implies that when academic staff succeed in their job, the entire quality of education is assured and maintained. Atanda (2016) and Atanda (2014) found that compensation and welfare packages promote the task performance of academic staff.

The result of hypothesis two as indicated in table 2 revealed that exposure to new opportunities relates significantly to quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. This finding was in consonant with Ekpiken and Asuquo (2015) who found out that a positive relationship exists between funding of in-service training and high productivity for quality assurance. This means that every academic staff needs new knowledge, skills and opportunities for professional growth leading to the achievement of educational quality and quality assurance. Tulgan cited in Ndifon (2017) maintained that teachers want to be exposed to new opportunities, and having their job recognized, as a result, they would maximize opportunities to showcase their creative talents. Akeke and Ofem (2016) observed that the organization has the opportunity to provide need-based training and education to its staff to enable them to become competent in handling their tasks. In consonant with this, Etor and Osim (2014) found that a positive relationship exists between providing opportunities for training and quality assurance in school. This indicates that quality can only be assured when academic staff duly implement the curriculum and for them to function efficiently, they need to be exposed to new knowledge to boost their morale. Babalola (2009) observed that the managers' main task is to develop a productive workplace with and through people. Also, Udofot (2005) averred that teachers need relevant skills and specific knowledge of the subject matter to teach effectively.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that academic staff empowerment variables such as compensation and exposure to new opportunities correlate positively with quality assurance in Colleges of Education in Cross River State, Nigeria. More so, empowerment is imperative in achieving educational quality and the entire quality assurance in Colleges of Education.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. academic staff compensational benefits should be considered a priority in Colleges of Education.
2. Academic staff should constantly be trained in both content and pedagogy
3. Promotion of academic staff should be well planned and implemented with financial benefits.

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